

E-commerce Adopting TOE Model by SMEs in Jordan

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Abstract

The objective of this research is to study the technology, organization and environment factors, which affect e-commerce SMEs in Jordan. This research is driven by the fact that e-commerce is still a long way behind the acceptance by large firms, especially in developing countries such as Jordan. However, companies, like SMEs, are forced to engage in e-commerce, to survive in this new economic era of knowledge. The researchers have evaluated the model and related hypotheses using SPSS to measure using the Technology, Organization and Environment (TOE) as the theoretical context. The findings of a survey of 121 small and medium-sized businesses in Jordan suggest that SMEs have the greatest possible effect on e-commerce adoption, on technical preparedness, management support and government support. The beta value is measured, and the R2 value is 0.691, reflecting 69.1% of the variance of e-commerce. Study contributions and outcomes are discussed, along with limitations and future recommendations.

Introduction

The digital age has been quickly moving, offering policy makers both opportunities and challenges. The size of market opportunities has changed to 10 or even 20 times that of the conventional channel. Also, people from all across the world will enter bigger markets. The digital channel offers sophisticated tools to engage the public, recognize clients, raise revenue, and increase quality and productivity in many fields. Companies must first qualify as digital, be creative in designing appealing goods, take price into account and use a digital E-C platform to win the competition (Lestari, 2019). E-C regarded the most important medium to be optimized, and even social media offer unique features that allow people to promote and sell goods online. Understanding one-on-one actions in E-C adoption can be a valuable tool for decision-makers to build a superior plan for competitive growth and for policymakers to devise genuine policies. While the government is paying special attention, the acceptance of E-C by Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs) remains a long way behind E-C by large firms (Alam et al., 2011; Chiliya, 2011; Rita & John, 2015; Salma, 2020). This raises the question of the exact factors influencing SMEs in their E-C adoption. The response is significant, because it is well recognized that SMEs play a large role in economic growth in every country in the world. Not only in numbers but also in terms of provision of employment, they make important contributions (Alraja et al., 2020; Kotelnikov, 2007; Talukder et al., 2020). Their contribution to the income and welfare of the household is recognized as a driver of innovation and economic improve, capacity for the individual and self-confidence, political stability and social change, distributary and democracy or development goals (Kotelnikov, 2007). SMEs play a more significant role in developed countries, particularly when it comes to poverty and unemployment reduction (Alraja et al., 2020; Sharma et al., 2020). This will have a direct impact on a country's economic growth through the sufficient and successful development of SMEs. The Government of Jordan has placed a lot of effort into setting up departments relevant to government, assigning funding, setting up an E-C system of \$13 billion, and so forth. This indicates that the government is highly concerned about the growth of e-commerce. SMEs play an important role in their countries in many developing countries, with SMUs serving as the country's financial backbone. In Jordan, 95.1% of companies are SMEs, and approximately 23% of Gross Domestic Products (GDP) and 41% of total jobs are employed (Alzoubi, 2018; Sharma et al., 2020; Salma, 2020). A thorough analysis of the current research, however, shows that only few empirical studies on the adoption of E-C by SMEs have been carried out. It is important to explore this topic further in view of the great interest. This paper therefore explores the acceptance of E-C by SMEs empirically. The section on E-C adoption by the small and medium-sized companies provides an important literature analysis of current empirical studies. The next segment provides a study of the structure and hypothesis for technology-organization-environment (TOE). The methodology and the findings respectively are followed in the third and fourth chapter. In addition, section 6 includes a discussion on study, contributions, shortcomings, and future research directions. In section seven we shall conclude.

2. Literature Review and Hypotheses

Rogers (1983) has two sets of structures for Diffusion of Creativity (DOI). This system gets some criticism from experts after some years, arguing that it only focuses on people, who are unable to describe some phenomena in the organization. Another collection of frameworks was introduced by Rogers, (1983) that can provide a clear picture of the process of organizational adoption, there are three components within this organizational structure, I leader characteristic: attitude to change, etc. (ii) internal organizational structure: business size, centralization, formalization, etc. and (iii) external organizational frameworks such as open system. To research information system studies, Tornatzky & Klein, (1990) developed a method called the environmental technical organization framework. This framework is similar to the DOI framework of Rogers (1983) and has 3 parts in this framework: I a technical context; (ii) an internal and external technology characteristic linked to the company; (ii) an organizational context: descriptive measure of, for example, organization size, capital, etc.; TOE is common because the Innovation Framework diffusion is consistent (Alzoubi M. I., 2018; Alzoubi & Alzoubi, 2019; Tornatzky & Klein, 1990). The second explanation is that, unlike other theoretical contexts, such as TAMs, the TOE Paradigm considers acceptance from multiple viewpoints; instead, it cannot describe such phenomena from an entity or environmental perspective, thereby allowing the study target to be partial and incorrect. These are the possible factors which may cause E-C practices to be successful or not.

2.1 Technological Factors

The technical background refers to factors that affect the use of E-C technology, such as relative advantages and usability. The perceived advantage refers to the degree to which ecommerce technology will deliver the organization's future benefits (Tiago & Maria, 2010; Lestari, 2019). Enhanced management awareness of the relative benefits of implementing E-C increases the likelihood that the organization can devote those resources for the implementation of E-C technology such as management resources, financial resources, and technical resources. Compatibility also applies to how adequate E-C is with technology infrastructure, culture, value, and market practices already present in the organization (Ali et al., 2019). In an organization, an idea is readily adopted, whether it is compatible with the existing principles of an organization and can satisfy the needs of the organization (Rogers, 1983). Therefore, the following hypotheses are:

H1: Relative advantage positively influence the E-C adoption by the SME

H2: Compatibility positively influences the E-C adoption by the SME

2.2 Organizational Factors

The market background refers to the features of the company that can affect the use of E-C technology. Technology readiness is a major factor in the adoption of E-C by SMEs as one of the organizational contexts suggested in this report. Technology readiness refers to how much E-C adoption will benefit the technology infrastructure, related systems and technical skills in companies (Nugroho et al., 2017). The availability of technology comprises technical infrastructure and IT human capital (Alraja et al., 2020; Zhu & Kraemer, 2005), both of which are really required if e-business is to be part of the value chain (Tiago & Maria, 2010). The greater the organization's technical readiness, the more likely it would use IT and vice versa. Management support is also a determinant factor of E-C adoption by SMEs in their organizational sense. The Concept of Management Support as a 'engagement ensures adequate resources for innovation' according to Prem kumar and Roberts (1999). Secondly, Salma, (2020) described management support as "providing essential motivational and engagement for the successful introduction of innovation and the more likely use of E-C technology". The second definition focuses on motivation. Thus, in this study it is hypothesized that:

H3: Technology readiness positively influences the E-C adoption by the SME

H4: Management support positively influences the E-C adoption by the SME

2.3 Environmental Context

External effect like pressure from government assistance and competitive pressure, which affect E-C adoption, are the environmental factors. In this study, the pressure from competitors is referred to by the degree of the industry's pressure from competitors (Rita & John, 2015; Zhu & Kraemer, 2005). Companies would be required to accept E-C technologies more broadly to achieve competitive advantages if they start using e-commerce. Therefore, the greater rivalry in the market, the greater the likelihood of the greater usage of E-C (Zhu & Kraemer, 2005). Sharma et al., (2020) stated that the decision by organizations, consumers, suppliers and trading partners to implement new technology could be pressure from an uncertainty climate and governments. Government plays an important role in fostering E-C in developing countries. The government had dedicated 13 billion to the enhancement of E-C and the system in Jordan (Alzoubi M. I., 2018), in addition to the implementation of a range of cyber-laws to protect users. For example, (b) Digital signals, (b) Telemedicine, (c) Copyright, (d) Computer crime, (e) Payment system, (f) Multimedia, (g) Electronic Government Operation, I Personal Information. The government support noticed by Sutanonpaiboon and Pearson (2006) Omar et al (2011) has no effect on adoption of e-commerce. Hence, these explanations lead to the following hypotheses:

H5: Government support positively influences the E-C adoption by the SME

H6: Competitor pressure positively influences the E-C adoption by the SME

3. Methodology

Jordanian companies were chosen as the target group of this study as the research unit for this experiment. Easy random sampling was applied, and the lists of target participants are registered members on the SME website. The sample size of the population has two thumb laws. According to Chin (1998), the researcher uses the 10 cases thumb rule per predictor, whereby the sample size overall is 10 times as wide as the two options: (1) the most frequently indicated block, or (2) the most independent variable that influences it. This research will explore possible factors affecting adoption of E-C in Jordan. A quantitative approach is used for gathering information from individual interviewees and 290 survey questionnaires are used. The target respondents are company owners, senior administrators, managers, or individuals with the authority to make organizational decisions. The distribution and data collection process took place over a 60-day period. Some of the filtering used in this research include (i) vendors interested in adopting or potential adopters; (ii) non-interest vendors or non-adopters and (iii) not in the relevant sector; except, in addition, nine empty answered questionnaires were replied, on the basis of the rationale given by the respective tenants, some of the commercial lots rented by vendors for the respective tenants. 121 datasets are available and used for study, which are 41.74% response rate, after applying the above filtering criteria.

3.1 Reliability and Validity

The assessment of the accuracy between multiple measurements of the variable is related to the reliability analysis. As for the validity test, it concerns the extent to which the construction is symbolized exactly by a set of measures or a scale (Hair, 2017). The degree to which an instrument's measure is expected or what the researcher wants to measure was clarified by Blumberg et al. (2005) in its validity. To calculate the reliability of the instrument, the Cronbach alpha coefficient was used. As Hair et al., (1998) suggested, values should be higher than the recommended 0.60 value for all indices or dimensional scales. The alpha results of the Cronbach are shown in the table for separate and dependent variables (1).

Table 1. Cronbach alpha for the TOE and E-C

Variables	Number of items	Cronbach Alpha
Relative advantage	6	0.974
Compatibility	4	0.891
Technology readiness	7	0.902
Management support	5	0.885
Government support	3	0.954
Competitor pressure	3	0.958
Adoption	5	0.897

The Cronbach alpha coefficients were greater than 0.60 for all of the variables measured. This indicates the composite measure's reliability. In addition, the studies have already verified and applied the elements chosen to calculate the independent and dependent variables. Therefore, this analysis strengthens the validity of the articles. In addition, the business faculty of 5 Jordanian universities studied questionnaires.

4. Hypotheses Testing Results

This study examines the impact of technology factors (relative advantage and compatibility), organizational factors (technology readiness and management support), and environmental factors (government support and competitor pressure) on the adoption of E-C among companies in Jordan. Therefore, for hypothesis testing, the multiple regression approach was applied. The value of the significance level (alp-level) of 0.05 was also selected in this analysis. In addition, the probability value (p-value) derived from the statistical hypothesis test is known to be the decisive rule for null hypothesis rejection (Creswell, 2009). The p-value obtained is smaller than or equal to the alpha-level, meaning that the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is supported. On the other hand, the p-value obtained higher than the alpha-level indicates failure to reject the null hypothesis, although it will not accept the alternative hypothesis. The normality of the independent variables and the non-presence of the multi co-linearity problem were also tested in this research (a case of multiple regression in which the independent variables have high correlation themselves). The majority of the values inside the normality-satisfactory ranges (i.e., -1.0 to +1.0) were proposed by Pallant (2005). Therefore, this research also investigated the skewness and the inflation factor variance (VIF). In the table, the results are shown (2).

Table 2. Skewness and VIF for the independent variables

Variables	Skewness	VIF
Relative advantage	-0.55	2.71
Compatibility	0.61	1.56
Technology readiness	-0.23	1.45
Management support	0.52	1.69
Government support	0.36	2.41
Competitor pressure	-0.45	2.11

Table 2 indicates that the skew values were within the standard value range (-1.0 to +1.0). This indicates the normality of the data from the independent variables. VIF values seemed to be lower than the critical value (10). This implies that multi-co-linearity among the independent variables is not an issue.

5. Conceptual Framework

The main purpose of this study was to evaluate the factors that are regarded as connected with E-C performance. Six factors from the related literature were found in this analysis. Moreover, in this research, a conceptual model was created. This model looks at E-C adoption at the company level. The study structure was based on a theoretical framework of Tornatzky and Fleischer's technology-organization-external (TOE) (1990). This study aims to define the factors associated with E-C performance. Therefore, instead of the ordered regression model, this analysis chose a linear regression.

5.1 Hypothesis

In this report, the research question is about the relationship between the TOE factors and the growth of E-C between companies in Jordan. In order to explore the relationship between dependent and independent variables the research conducted analysis of linear regression. Table (3) illustrates the effects of hypothesis tests.

Table 3. Result for the study model (a, b, and c)

A)

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.832 ^a	0.701	0.691	0.06620

B)

Anova

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	59.032	8	7.487	131.189	0.000
Residual	4.374	378	.007		
Total	63.406	386			

C)

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.426	.061		7.658	0.000
Relative advantage	.083	.71	.226	6.770	0.002
Compatibility	.081	.31	.127	3.512	0.512
Technology readiness	.289	.107	.531	4.541	0.000
Management support	.184	.102	.517	6.554	0.001
Government support	.220	.015	.490	5.254	0.000
Competitor pressure	.245	.018	.515	6.874	0.411

In the table above, the modified R square value is 0,691 for the regression model (cf. Table One) meaning that 69.1% of the variances of E-C acceptance are collectively explained by the independent variable and 0,00 is the significance value of the regression trend (cf. Table Two). Table Three shows the strong association with the adoption of E-C with all independent variables except usability and competitor pressures. However, only four of these variables have a value below 0.05, which is relative advantage, technical readiness, support for management and the support of the government; the others have a value above 0.05. The six variables proposed as factors decisive for the adoption of E-C by SMEs in this study are expressed in these. H1, H3, H4 and H5 are all completely endorsed in this review.

6. Discussion and Conclusion

In this analysis, the TOE-Framework was used to assess factors that influence the adoption of E-C by SMEs in Jordan. Two variables have been established in this study in technical contexts that impact the e-compatibility of Jordanian SMEs. In this analysis it has been found that the relative benefit has a positive and substantial connection to the E-C adoption, which means that the relative benefit is a driving factor for the E-C adoption by Jordanian SMEs. H1 is also completely endorsed in this report. This result correlates to previous studies (Alam et al., 2011; Alraja et al., 2020). The correlation with the adoption of E-C is also positive, but statistically important. H2 is not sponsored, therefore. This is not in line with the results of El-Gohary research, which were conductible under Ali et al., (2019); Salma, (2020) and El-Gohary, (2012). One reason for the outcome may be that SMEs do not have as many applications, especially in Jordan, and so are not worries that their applications are integrated with the new application (Ramdani et al., 2013). The study is planned as determinants of E-C adoption by SMEs in Jordan, as well as technical readiness and management support which are defined as an organizational background. However, it was found that the findings of the Regression Study are consistent with previous studies including Tiago & Maria, (2010); Ramdani et al., (2013) and that technology readiness and management support are positive and strongly linked to the E-C adoption. In particular, Salma, (2020) concluded that the most important factor in the E-C adoption of companies in developing countries, like Jordan, was technical readiness and management support. In this study two variables which are competitive pressure and public support are classed as environmental contexts and are defined as factors affecting E-C technology in small- and medium-sized businesses in Jordan. However, this research has a positive and meaningful association between government funding and the adoption of e-commerce, while competitor pressure is not statistically significant. H5 is fully supported and H6 is not supported in this report. This finding is consistent with previous research, for example, the sample size is also limited and cannot generalize the outcome to the entire population. The findings are small. It also allows a free distribution, the R2 value can be defined by removing the outliers. The program has some limitation. In conclusion, the study addressed questions from the research and found the possible factors for E-C in Jordan. Relevant lessons can be learned both for small and medium-sized enterprises and for small and medium-sized firms in developed countries as opposed to developing countries.

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